

Sample Name: dNTPs ATP mix 5uM

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=====
Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                      Seq. Line :    2
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                 Location  :    2
Injection Date  : 12/10/2020 12:48:06 PM      Inj       :    1
                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
Method          : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2020-12-10
                  12-20-56\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed    : 12/10/2020 10:10:22 AM by SYSTEM
=====

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Fraction Information
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No Fractions found.
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Area Percent Report
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Sorted By      :      Signal
Multiplier     :      1.0000
Dilution       :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs

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Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	1.889	VV R	0.1512	39.48849	3.37228	2.3945
2	2.144	VB	0.1314	90.26960	10.15080	5.4737
3	10.540	BV R	0.1762	180.36656	15.71045	10.9370
4	12.987	BV R	0.1702	367.59540	33.51352	22.2901
5	14.823	BB	0.1768	190.14568	16.66883	11.5300
6	16.277	BB	0.1794	405.44711	35.22550	24.5853

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Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
7	18.432	BB	0.1840	375.82962	31.57020	22.7894

Totals : 1649.14246 146.21158

```

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*** End of Report ***

```